

Access and Usage of Electronic Resources by the Faculty Members, Students and Research Scholars of Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Tiruvannamalai “Thiruvalluvar University”– A Study

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ABSTRACT: A survey becomes carried out is conducted at the Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Tiruvannamalai Affiliated with Thiruvalluvar University. A total quantity of 271 respondents questionnaires is issued to the respondents and 231 respondents replied and Submit the Researcher for study Members were selected and their responses turned into obtained with the assistance of the questionnaire. The findings show that customers the use of e-resources responsiveness approximately e-resources encourages users to apply such sources to the very best and the users are the usage of Department and domestic extra for getting access to the statistics E- resources turned into visible from the lower in range of revealed documents in contrast to the increase in the quantity of digital resource.

KEYWORDS: E-resources, Electronic Information, Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Tiruvannamalai, Use of E-resources Use of Electronic Services.

INTRODUCTION

The emergence of the internet as a cutting-edge medium of statistics garage and shipping represents a revolution, on the way to having an extended-lasting impact on the virtual e-book and delivery of records machines in the twenty-first century. The tendencies in the records era have brought e-journals as a boon to research networks, which can be turning into a vital supply for scholarly communication. The ultimate decade has witnessed a growing competition to deliver new digital data offerings to loads of heaps of customers. The information of the technologies of information and communiqué is specifically crucial as it refers to a place of the information generated thru men and that has been produced to make feasible exchange forms and contributors of the family they are essential to assist the technique of the modern-day globalization that ends within the statistics society.

Digital media has supplied many opportunities and possibilities for presenting faster and quicker getting proper entry to facts at the global diploma. The generation for virtual publishing, digital garage, processing and transport of facts which includes text and photos This is the paper of Electronic belongings the clients acquire the facts from the Library thru virtual sources the clients Learning and acquire the, it impacts on the gathering of print and digital assets its attention maximum of the clients, and the locations in which the customers are having access to these sources

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Subbulakshmi (2017) Electronics sources may have a main effect on the great of the research work. The paper and try have been made to find the use of digital resources by using faculty contributors and Research students of Arts and Science College affiliated with Alagappa University Karaikudi. They take a look at changes carried out with the assistance of the questionnaire. The highest number of respondents 203 have to have M. Phil qualification observed through 184, that's the second highest reaction was having a Ph.D., and the most effective forty-six had a PG qualification only.

Viji (2018) The use of e-sources by the school individuals of Affiliated Arts and Science Colleges of Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, so one can study the exposure of school members to e-resources. The authors look into the use of e-sources by way of the faculty contributors of Affiliated Arts and Science Colleges of Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, through a

survey primarily based on a based questionnaire. This takes a look at confirming that the faculty participants are conscious of the e-resources and various types of e-resources.

Neetika Sharma (2019) the wide-ranging use of statistics and conversation technology, particularly the World Wide Web, has introduced big adjustments in the way facts are generated, saved, and accessed. With the fast improvement and use of the net and internet-based tools and technologies the important development, this is taking area in libraries is full-size availability and use of numerous styles of e-resources which includes online database, OPAC, CD-ROM databases, online portals in preferred or challenge wise. Now libraries and records centers spend increasing the budget for subscribing e resources, even if shrinking budgets of the libraries. This paper deals with a examination on the focus, accessibility, and use by using the faculty participants and studies pupils of 5 disciplines of the social technological know-how of Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, Haryana

OBJECTIVE

To identify the category clever getting access to online sources

To look at and hobby Thoughts of the respondents closer to the use of e-Resources

To find out the resources of recognition and the reason for its get the right of entry to

METHODOLOGY

The gift examination has taken into consideration the Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Tiruvannamalai for the related evaluation. The pattern of the survey incorporates Faculty participants, studies students, and P.G Students selected and an established 271 questionnaire was changed into given to them, then answers questionnaire collected from the 231 respondents. Consciousness, motive, and blessings related to using e-resources, prominent areas, and motives for accessing e- resources. In addition troubles and difficulties were additionally analyzed

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Table -1 Gender wise use the library

S.L	Use Library for Study	Gender		Total
		Male	Female	
1	Yes	178 79.8%	45 20.2%	223 100.0%
2	No	7 87.5%	1 12.5%	8 100.0%
	Total	185	46	231

As visible from Table Gender wise Use Library for Study male are 178 respondents Yes 79.8 Percentage . Female 45 respondents are Yes 20.2 percent total number of 223 respondents. Gender wise Use Library for Study male is 7 respondents Yes 87.5 Percentage. Female 1 respondents is no 12.5 percent a total number of 8 respondents. The total number of respondents male was 185 and female 46 out of 231 respondents were.

Table – 2 Status wise Use internet experience

S.L	Type of the Respondents	Use internet experience				Total
		One Year	Two Years	Three Years	More than Four Years	
1	Faculty Members	28 38.9%	9 12.5%	11 15.3%	24 33.3%	72 100.0%
2	Research Scholar	2 20.0%	3 30.0%	1 10.0%	4 40.0%	10 100.0%
3	PG Student	106 71.1%	16 10.7%	16 10.7%	11 7.4%	149 100.0%
	Total	136	28	28	39	231

The table Explain Respondents wise Use internet experience of Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College total Years are Use internet experience by the faculty members of one Years are 28 respondents 38.9 Percentage Research Scholar one year Using 2 respondents 20 percentage PG Student one year 106 respondents 71.1 percentage and total numbers of 136 respondents . Faculty Members are Two year Using 9 respondents 12.5 Percentage. Research Scholar one year Using 3 respondents 30 percentage PG Student Two year 16 respondents 10.7 percentage and total numbers of 28 respondents Faculty Members are Three year Using 11respondents 15.3 Percentage . Research Scholar one year Using 1 respondents 10 percentage PG Student Three year 16 respondents 10.7 percentage and total numbers of 28 respondents Faculty Members are More than Four Years Using 24 respondents 33.3 Percentage . Research Scholar one year Using 4 respondents 40 percentage PG Student More than Four Years 11 respondents 7.4 percentage and total numbers of 39 respondents. This table reveals that the overall Faculty Members 72 respondents, Research Scholar overall 10 respondents and PG Student 149 respondents Use internet experience.

Table – 3 Gender wise e-resources accessed and downloaded easier and faster

S.L	Gender	e-resources accessed and downloaded easier and faster		Total
		Agree	Disagree	
1	Male	181 97.8%	4 2.2%	185 100.0%
2	Female	46 100.0%	0 .0%	46 100.0%
	Total	227	4	231

As visible from Table Gender wise Accessed and Downloaded Easier and Faster male are 181 respondents agree 97.8 Percentage .Female 46 respondents are agree 100 percentage total numbers of 227 respondents .Gender wise Accessed and Downloaded Easier and Faster male are 4 respondents Disagree 2.2 Percentage .Female respondents are Disagree 0 percentage total numbers of 4 respondents .Total number of respondents male 185 and female 46 out of 231 respondents

Table – 4 Respondents wise e-resources accessed and downloaded easier and faster

SL	Type of the Respondents	e-resources accessed and downloaded easier and faster		Total
		Agree	Disagree	
1	Faculty Members	71 98.6%	1 1.4%	72 100.0%
2	Research Scholar	10 100.0%	0 .0%	10 100.0%
3	PG Student	146 98.0%	3 2.0%	149 100.0%
	Total	227	4	231

The table shows Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Respondents wise E-Resources can be Accessed and Downloaded Easier and Faster Faculty Members are 71 respondents agree 98.6 Percentage. Research Scholar 10 respondents are Yes 100 percentage PG Student 146 respondents are Yes 98 percentage and total numbers of 227 respondents .Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Respondents wise E-Resources can be Accessed and Downloaded Easier and Faster. Faculty Members are 1 respondents disagree 1.4 Percentage. Research Scholar 0 respondents are Disagree 0 percentage PG Student 3 respondents are Disagree 2.0 percentage and total numbers of 4 no answered respondents. Total number of 231 respondents of Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College.

Table – 5 Advantages of accessing e-resources gender wise

S.L.	Gender	advantages of accessing e-resources					Total
		Less time in searching	Availability of the journal much before the print copy	Real-time usage Easy accessibility	Downloadin g facility	Author can be contacted directly through e-mail	
1	Male	80 43.2%	30 16.2%	24 13.0%	32 17.3%	19 10.3%	185 100.0%
2	Female	20 43.5%	6 13.0%	9 19.6%	4 8.7%	7 15.2%	46 100.0%
		100	36	33	36	26	231

The table Explains Gender wise Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science Advantages of accessing E-Resources Less time in searching male 80 respondents 43.2 Percentage. Female Less time in searching 20 respondents 43.5 percent and a total number of 100 respondents. Male Availability of the journal much before the print copy 30 respondents 16.2 Percentage Female Availability of the journal much before the print copy 6 respondents 13.0 percentage and the total number of 36 respondents, Real-time usage

Easy accessibility male 24 respondents 13 Percentage Female Real-time usage Easy accessibility 6 respondents 13.0 percent and total numbers of 33 respondents, Downloading facility

Male Downloading facility 32 respondents 17.3 Percentage Downloading facility Female 4 respondents 8.7 percent and a total number of 36 respondents, Author can be contacted directly through e-mail male 19 respondents 10.3 Percentage Author can be contacted directly through e-mail Female 7 respondents 15.2 percent and a total number of 26 respondents, This table reveals that overall Male 185 respondents, female overall 46 respondents out of 231 respondents.

Table - 6 status wise advantages of accessing e-resources

S.L	Type of the Respondents	advantages of accessing e-resources					Total
		Less time in searching	Availability of the journal much before the print copy	Real-time usage Easy accessibility	Downloading facility	Author can be contacted directly through e-mail	
1	Faculty Members	32 44.4%	22 30.6%	9 12.5%	7 9.7%	2 2.8%	72 100.0%
2	Research Scholar	5 50.0%	2 20.0%	1 10.0%	2 20.0%	0	10 100.0%
3	PG Student	63 42.3%	12 8.1%	23 15.4%	27 18.1%	24 16.1%	149 100.0%
		100	36	33	36	26	231

The table Explain Respondents wise Shanmuga Industries Arts and Science College Faculty Members Less time in searching 32 respondents 44.4 Percentage Research Scholar Less time in searching 5 respondents 50. Percentage PG Student Less time in searching 63 respondents 42.3 percent and the total number of 100 respondents. Faculty Members are Availability in the journal much before the print copy 22 respondents 30.6 Percentage. Research Scholar Availability of the journal much before the print copy 2 respondents 20 percentage PG Student Availability of the journal much before the print copy 12 respondents 8.1 percentage and total number of 36 respondents Faculty Members are Real-time usage Easy accessibility 9 respondents 12.5 Percentage. Research Scholar Real-time usage Easy accessibility 1 respondent 10 percentage PG Student Real-time usage Easy accessibility 23 respondents 15.4 percentage and the total number of 33 respondents. Faculty Members are Downloading facility 7 respondents 9.7 Percentage. Research Scholar Downloading facility 2 respondents 20 percent.PG Student Downloading facility 27 respondents 18.1 percent and a total number of 36 respondents. And Faculty Members are Authors can be contacted directly through e-mail 2 respondents 2.8 Percentage. Research Scholar Author can be contacted directly through e-mail no respondents zero percentage.PG Student Author can be contacted directly through e-mail 24 respondents 16.1 percentage and total numbers of 26 respondents. This table reveals that the overall Faculty Members are 72 respondents, Research Scholars overall 10 respondents, and PG Students 149 respondents out of 231.

FEATURE OF E-RESOURCES

This Paper explains the Gender wise Library User and Respondents' wise User analysis It is found that the positive response about the convenience of using years was more represented in, Advantages of accessing E-Resources it is founded on the respondents and the respondents downloaded E-Resources Accessed and Downloaded Easier and Faster show this Paper. Library User category and respondents wise explained in this Paper.

CONCLUSION

Faculty members Research scholar and PG Students are heavily dependent on e resources for their required information and to keep themselves up-to-date in their subject area. the e-resources which may have more importance in future as Faculty members Research scholar and PG Students are access more and more e resources in their respective area or personal The study reveals that the Faculty members Research scholar and PG Students of Shanmuga Industries Arts And Science College Tiruvannamalai Affiliated by Thiruvalluvar University respondents are using the available e-resources with satisfaction.

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